

Synthesis of Possible Analgesic Agents

S. MUKHERJEE AND B. PATHAK

Department of Applied Chemistry, Calcutta University, Calcutta-9

(Manuscript received 31 July 1972; accepted 10 November 1972)

A number of N-alkyl hexahydro indeno (1,2-b) pyridines were prepared for pharmacological interest, by reductive amination of ethyl 1-keto 2-indanyl cyano methyl malonate followed by alkylation with alkyl halides. These compounds did not however show any analgesic activity.

SEVERAL workers attempted to co-relate the structure activity relationship of morphine and analogous compounds¹⁻⁴. It is believed that in substituted piperidines the phenyl group disposed axially at the 4-position of the piperidine moiety is favourable for the development of analgesic activity. Braenden *et al.*⁵ however reported that a piperidine derivative (I) in which the phenyl group is equatorially disposed exhibited high activity. It therefore appears that the exact conformation in aryl piperidines may not be the essential requirement for the development of analgesic activity.

In the present investigation a series of N-alkyl hexahydro indeno (1,2-b) pyridine (II) derivatives have been prepared to examine their analgesic activity. Compound (II) is capable of existing in two isomeric forms (IIa & IIb). However they have not been separated.

Raney Ni-catalyst yields 4-di-carboxyethyl-hexahydro-indeno (1,2-b)-pyridine (II; R = H). Alkylation of the secondary amine with alkyl halide has resulted in the formation of desired products. No attempt has however been made to separate the isomers.

Pharmacology: These compounds were kindly tested by Smith Kline & French Laboratories, Philadelphia, on mice using a modified D'Amour and Smith method as modified by Bass and Vander Brook^{7,8}. None of these compounds has shown significant analgesic activity at dose level of 50 mg/kg. body weight.

Experimental

Ethyl 1-keto 2-indanyl cyano methyl malonate (III) : Ethyl 1-keto 2-indanyl malonate (29 g, 0.1 mol) was

I

II

IIa

IIb

III

Sodio ethyl 1-keto 2-indanyl malonate⁶ on condensation with chloro-acetonitrile yields ethyl 1-keto 2-indanyl cyano methyl malonate (III). The latter on hydrogenation under high pressure in presence of

added dropwise to molecular sodium (2.3 g, 0.1 mol) in thiophene free benzene (250 ml) under stirring. When the whole of sodium reacted, chloromethyl cyanide (7.6 g, 0.1 mol) dissolved in benzene (20 ml)

was added under stirring and the mixture was refluxed for 12 hr. The mass was then cooled, treated with water, and the benzene layer on distillation yielded the desired material, b.p. 190–95°C/0.15 mm; yield 15 g. It crystallised from aqueous ethanol (50%), m.p. 69°C. (Found: C, 65.9; H, 6.0; N, 4.5; calc. for $C_{18}H_{19}O_5N$: C, 65.6; H, 5.7; N, 4.2%).

4-Di-carboxyethyl 1,1a,2,3,4,4a-hexahydro 5H-indeno (1,2-b)pyridine (II; R = H): The above cyano compound (III; 30 g) in absolute alcohol (100 ml) was heated in presence of Raney Ni catalyst and hydrogen at 100°C and 100 atm. pressure for 6 hr. The product was then filtered, alcohol was removed

in a sealed tube in oil bath at 100 to 110°C for 8 hr. Excess of alkyl halide was removed and the product was basified with cold alkali and the base was extracted out with ether, converted into hydrochloride and crystallised from a mixture of benzene and pet. ether (60–80°C). Properties of the hydrochlorides are recorded in Table 1.

Acknowledgement

The authors are indebted to Messrs. Smith Kline & French Laboratories, Philadelphia, U.S.A., for kindly providing with the test report.

TABLE I. 4-DI-CARBOXYETHYL-1-ALKYL 1,1A,2,3,4,4A-HEXAHYDRO 5H-INDENO (1,2-B) PYRIDINE

R	Alkyl halide used	M.P. (°C) of hydrochloride	Formula	N%		Cl%	
				Calc.	Found	Calc.	Found
1. CH_3	CH_3I	178	$C_{15}H_{26}O_4NCl$	3.8	4.2	9.7	9.9
2. C_2H_5	C_2H_5I	172	$C_{20}H_{26}O_4NCl$	3.6	3.7	9.3	9.7
3. $n-C_3H_7$	C_3H_7I	116	$C_{21}H_{30}O_4NCl$	3.5	3.7	8.9	9.0
4. $n-C_4H_9$	C_4H_9Br	145	$C_{22}H_{32}O_4NCl$	3.4	3.8	8.6	8.7
5. $n-C_5H_{11}$	$C_5H_{11}Br$	174	$C_{23}H_{34}O_4NCl$	3.3	3.6	8.3	8.7
6. $n-C_6H_{13}$	$C_6H_{13}Br$	161	$C_{24}H_{36}O_4NCl$	3.2	3.5	8.1	8.4

by distillation from the filtrate and to the residual mass in benzene was passed HCl gas. The hydrochloride was filtered out, dissolved in water, basified with cold NaOH solution and extracted with ether. The amine distilled at 180–85°C/0.35 mm; yield 12 g. Hydrochloride crystallised from ethyl acetate, m.p. 229°C. (Found: C, 61.5; H, 7.2; N, 4.2; calc. for $C_{18}H_{24}O_4NCl$: C, 61.1; H, 6.8; N, 3.9%).

4-Di-carboxyethyl 1-alkyl 1,1a,2,3,4,4a-hexahydro 5H-indeno (1,2-b) pyridine (II; R = Alkyl): A mixture of the above hexahydro indeno pyridine (II; R = H; 0.01 mol) and alkyl halide (0.02 mol) was heated

References

1. A. H. BECKETT and A. F. CASY, *J. Pharm. Pharmacol.*, 1954, **6**, 986.
2. A. ZIERING and J. LEB, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1947, **12**, 911.
3. E. E. SMISSMAN and M. STEINMAN, *J. Med. Chem.*, 1966, **9**, 455.
4. P. S. PORTOGHESE, *J. Pharm. Sci.*, 1966, **55**, 865.
5. O. J. BRAENDEN, B. N. EDDY and H. HALBACH, *Bull. World Health Org.*, 1955, **13**, 937.
6. L. H. GROVES and G. A. SWAN, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1951, 867.
7. F. E. D'AMOUR and D. L. SMITH, *J. Pharmacol. Exptl. Therapy*, 1941, **72**, 74.
8. W. B. BASS and M. J. VANDERBROOK, *J. Amer. Pharm. Assoc. (Sci. Ed.)*, 1952, **41**, 569.